

Finding the implicit information asymmetry costs of R&D expenditures? A market-based approach

Sonik Mandal

Department of Accounting and Finance, Romain College of Business, Evansville, Indiana, USA-47712.

Abstract

This paper puts forward a novel way of finding the information asymmetry costs of a firm's R&D investments using a 5-step market-based approach. It then shows how to calculate the breakeven R&D expense, the dollar amount of R&D where the intangible benefits of R&D and the implicit information asymmetry costs of R&D are equal. Finally, the paper suggests some moderating factors that affect these costs and the breakeven R&D. I expect the benefits of R&D investments to start low and increase during the life of the project. On the contrary, information asymmetry costs should start high and then gradually fall. The shape of the two curves would be affected by various factors like industry, analyst following, firm size etc. Similar risk projects should have similar information asymmetry costs and break-even R&D expenditures, assuming market efficiency and rationally informed investors. Risk-averse managers worrying about the high information asymmetry costs of their R&D projects resulting in depressed stock prices for an extended period should find this research very enriching.

Keywords: R&D Investments, Information asymmetry costs, stock price, intangible assets.

How to Cite: Sonik Mandal. (2025). Finding the implicit information asymmetry costs of R&D expenditures? A market-based approach. *International Journal of Finance (IJFIN)*, 38(5), 57–67. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17234718>

1. INTRODUCTION

Firms' investment in R&D create intangible assets like patents, goodwill, trademarks, etc. (Lev and Sougiannis 1990; Eberhart, 2004; Chan et al. 2001). In return, investors reward the firms with a higher stock price in anticipation of these value-enhancing assets (Feeny and Rogers, 2001; Chan et al. 1990; Connolly and Hirschey, 1993). This is the benefit of R&D investments motivating managers to spend billions on R&D. But there is also a cost associated with when firms invest in R&D, which has not been properly investigated in the previous literature. We all know about the explicit dollar costs of an R&D, but there are implicit costs too. When firms invest in R&D, managers have better information about the projects compared to outside investors, or in other words, there is information asymmetry (Aboody and Lev, 2002). This causes investors to discount the stock prices at a higher discount rate, and the stock prices to decline (Eberhart et al. 2004; Kothari et al. 2002). This might cause managers to be risk averse and not take up a positive NPV R&D project and cause underinvestment, reducing the value of the firm (Myers and Majluf, 1984; Porter, 1992). The information asymmetry costs, and the subsequent sub-optimal R&D investment also causes agency issues (Jensen, 1986), managers' focusing on meeting compensation targets rather than focusing on their long-term R&D projects (Harter & Harikumar, 2004) and managers' meeting short term earnings target at the expense of long-term future of the firm (Graham et al. 2005; Baber et al. 1991). The finance literature has focused on calculating the benefits of R&D using any one of the intangible assets' valuation models, but the cost side calculation of R&D investment has been ignored.

In this paper, I propose a simple way to determine the implicit information asymmetry costs of a firm's R&D projects using a market-based approach, which has not been looked upon in the previous literature. Next, I try to determine the breakeven R&D expense where the costs and benefits of firms' R&D projects are equal. Then I discuss some moderating forces that might affect these costs and the breakeven R&D. I conclude by looking at some managerial implications based upon the costs and breakeven R&D & suggest some future research directions and point out some limitations.

2. THEORY

2.1. Information asymmetry costs

I start by talking about the implicit costs associated with investing in R&D. The costs I will be focusing on are incurred by the firm when it starts to make monetary investments and end a

few months after the last investment is made, assuming markets are mostly efficient. The costs of failure are not considered here as I am focusing on the future benefits and costs manifested in the share price when the firm makes those investments. For effective comparison, our duration is the period when the firm is spending dollars on R&D. Obviously some of the costs are tangible and are expensed as R&D in the income statement, which reduces the current net income thus discouraging many short-term profit-oriented managers to invest in R&D (Wahal and McConnell, 2000). In this paper, I am focusing on the implicit costs. All these types of costs can be grouped under information asymmetry since they originate due to the firms' R&D investments which the managers have more knowledge of relative to the outside investors. The costs cause the stock price to decline due to the uncertainty of the future cash flow of the project (explained in the next section). A question arises- why does higher R&D investments for a firm increase the information asymmetry? There are three reasons as mentioned in Aboody & Lev (2002). First, most of the cash flows from a R&D project come later in the investment's lifetime. Moreover, the cash flows are uncertain, this gives rise to information asymmetry where outside investors deem the firm as risky. Second, many R&D projects are novel and so there is no benchmark project to value them giving rise to information asymmetry. Finally, the value of the intangible assets created by the firm like trade secrets, brand, etc. are known with certainty by the management. Also, their values are not listed on the balance sheet; as a result, investors know less of these compared to the management giving rise to information asymmetry.

2.2. Intangible assets creation- benefits

International Accounting Standard 38 (International Accounting Standards Board, 1998) defines intangible assets as "an identifiable non-monetary asset without physical substance. An asset is a resource that is controlled by the entity as a result of past events and from which future economic benefits are expected to flow to the entity". It also mentions typical examples of intangible assets such as computer software, patents, copyrights, motion picture films, customer lists, mortgage servicing rights, fishing licenses, import quotas, franchises, customer or supplier relationships, customer loyalty, market share and marketing rights. Valuing intangible assets is difficult as they do not appear on the balance sheet. Fortunately, previous literature has identified a few approaches to value the intangibles like the one shown below by Lagrost et al., 2010. As my motivation of this paper is to find the information asymmetry costs, I do not detail these approaches in this paper.

(The image above is taken from Pastor et al. 2017)

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Determining the costs and benefits of a R&D project from the stock price-

As mentioned above, the costs that I am focusing on in this paper are the information asymmetry costs which cause the firm's stock price to decline. On the other hand, a firm's investment in R&D creates intangible assets like trademarks, brands, trade secrets, etc. which increases the future cash flow and raises the stock price. To determine the implicit costs, I proceed as follows-

Step 1- Using a multifactor asset pricing model like the APT or the multi-factor Fama French model, I control for the overall effects of the market & economy, and the abnormal excess return alpha of the regression will be the return due to firm specific factors. The cross-sectional OLS regression needs to be run after the firm's quarterly or annual earnings release, assuming semi- strong market efficiency. I repeat this regression every quarter if quarterly statements are used or every year if annual statements are used for the total number of years of the firm's investments. Many times, the market overreacts or underreacts to earnings release, so I do the regression 2-3 months after the release (this will depend upon various factors like firm's industry, disclosure levels, investors' optimism/pessimism about the firm, etc.).

Step 2- Obviously, the abnormal return will also be due to other favorable firm specific factors like increases in dividends, earnings, lower costs, new CEO, etc. To strip their effects from the R&D, I run a secondary regression with the abnormal returns from step 1 as the dependent variable and all other factors known to increase the share price as independent variables; the residual from this regression will be the abnormal return from R&D investments.

Step 3- Using the abnormal return from step 2, I can calculate the total real value created due to the project by multiplying the return with the investment of the project in that year.

¹The total value will consist of the benefits due to the expectation of the creation of the intangible assets but will be scaled down by the information asymmetry costs.

Step 4- To separate the benefits and costs from the total value, I can value the intangible assets that will be created from the firm's R&D projects using the various models that have been proposed in the past (Lagrost et al., 2010). This will be the benefits number to be used in finding the information asymmetry costs.

Step 5- To calculate the costs, I just subtract the total benefits from the total real value calculated which will be approximately equal to the information asymmetry costs. I repeat the benefits and costs calculation for every year or quarter (as mentioned in step 1) over the life of the firm's R&D projects².

3.2. Finding the optimal R&D investments

As a firm start investing in R&D projects, initially information asymmetry costs should be higher as investors have less knowledge of the project. As the project continues, these costs should fall as outside investors start to know more about the investment. On the contrary, total value creation from the R&D should start low during the initial years and then start to rise as investors build expectations of the benefits through the creation of the intangible assets. The point at which the benefits curve intersects the cost curve is the minimum dollar amount of R&D investments required for the project to be successful in terms of adding value to the share price. I can also locate the number of years from the start of the project when the benefits outweigh the costs. The minimum amount and the breakeven year would depend upon various factors like riskiness of the R&D project, size of the project, industry involved, etc. (I explain in the next section how each of these factors will change the shape of the curves and the breakeven R&D investments). Below is an example shown in Table 1 and a graphical representation depicted in Figure 1 to illustrate my point. I assume the firm invests 1 million R&D dollars every year for a period of 5 years. The abnormal return due to the R&D project is shown below in table 1, column 2 for each year (which can be calculated using the 5-step approach explained above). Multiplying the abnormal return due to the firm's R&D investments with each year's dollar R&D investment gives the total value increase manifested in the stock price due to the project each year (shown in column 3 in Table 1). The intangible assets benefits are then calculated separately using one

² The method above is used to calculate the information asymmetry costs of all R&D expenses of a firm. To find the costs of a particular project, I can find the costs before the project is undertaken and after the project is implemented. The difference will be the costs associated with a particular new project. This approach will be useful to find the information asymmetry costs of new projects/products which differ from the firm's core projects

of the many intangible asset models cited in the previous literature as shown in Table 1, column 4. As the full benefits of the intangible assets cannot be realized in the stock price due to the information asymmetry costs, I subtract the benefits from the total stock value to get the implicit costs of R&D (shown in column 5, Table 1). One important point to note looking at Table 1 is that information asymmetry costs turn positive in years 4 and 5. We can infer that at that time investors' have all knowledge of the firms' R&D projects and there is no more "information asymmetry" and based upon the information gathered about the firm's R&D investments in years 1-3, they add value to the stock price (in addition to the intangible asset benefits).

Next, I plot the stock value change, benefits and costs in the graph below as shown in Figure 1. I expect to see the stock value being negative when the firm first starts to invest in R&D due to the high information asymmetry costs. As the firm continues their investments, investors become more cognizant of the project and so the costs should fall. The benefits calculated from an asset model in contrast should start low and then rise since the creation of the intangible assets and subsequent investor perception of it is gradual over the time of the project. The point where the benefits and costs curves intersect is the break-even point (year) of R&D investments. Similar projects should have similar costs and benefits with different moderating factors affecting this relationship as discussed in the next section.

Table 1- Calculation of Information asymmetry costs of R&D investments

This table reports the dollar value of intangible assets benefits and information asymmetry costs of R&D expenditures for years 1-5 assuming \$1m investment in each year. I also assume the abnormal return values each year (can be calculated using the 5-step method described above) as shown in column 2. The total stock value increase shown in column 3 is calculated by multiplying the abnormal return with the \$1m investment each year. The benefits of R&D investment shown in column 4 is calculated by using any one of the intangible assets valuation models described in Lagrost et al. (2010). The information asymmetry costs as shown in column 5 is then determined by subtracting the benefits from the total dollar stock value increase.

Year	Abnormal return	Total stock value increase	Benefits	Information asymmetry Costs
1	-4%	-40000	10000	-50000
2	-2.50%	-25000	20000	-45000
3	-1%	-10000	30000	-40000
4	7.5%	75000	40000	35000
5	9%	90000	50000	40000

The figure below shows the costs, benefits and stock value change of firm's R&D investments based upon a \$1m annual R&D expenditures. The graph is drawn from values taken from Table 1 above

Figure 1: Costs, benefits and stock value change of R&D investments

3.3. Some moderating variables affecting the shape of the curves-

a) R&D disclosure-

I can expect firms with more disclosure to have lower information asymmetry costs (Coller and Yohn, 1997; Balakrishnan et al., 2014; Billings et al., 2015; Jones, 2007; Merkley, 2014) and so the cost curve will shift downward, and the breakeven R&D level should be lower (assuming benefits remain the same).

b) Analyst following-

Greater the analyst following of the stock, less the information asymmetry costs should be (Frankel and Li, 2004), and so the cost curve will shift downward and breakeven R&D should be lower.

c) Industry of the firm-

The break-even R&D point will depend upon the industry of the firm (reason why all previous research on R&D controls for industry effects). Firms in R&D intensive industries like pharmaceutical and biotechnology industry will have higher benefits as expectations of a new drug or product will drastically increase the value of the stock price.

But those firms will also try to keep secret the nature of their new product and so higher information asymmetry costs, thus the breakeven R&D point might increase, or decrease based upon the movement of the two curves. Other R&D-intensive industries like technology might not have a need to keep trade secrets, and so for those firms, benefits like rise relative to information asymmetry costs causing the breakeven R&D investment to decline.

d) Corporate social responsibility (CSR)-

Previous research has shown that CSR reduces information asymmetry costs (Cui et al., 2018; Lys et al., 2015; Cheng et al., 2014; Luo et al., 2014; Cao et al., 2013) and assuming the benefits stay the same, I expect the cost curve to decline and optimal R&D investment to come down.

e) Firm Size-

Greater the firm size, the more information asymmetry is expected to be (Seyhun, 1986; Lakonishok and Lee, 2001), and greater the break-even point of R&D expenses I expect.

f) Book-to-market value ratio-

Firms with high book to market value are usually distressed firms with high information asymmetry costs (Huddart and Ke, 2007) causing underinvestment and value decreasing projects. I expect higher break-even levels for the firm's R&D investment.

g) Advertising expenses-

The higher the advertising expenses, greater will be the information asymmetry (Joseph & Wintoki (2013) and more will be the breakeven point of the R&D investments.

h) Dividend payout policy-

Firms with high-dividend payouts should have lower information asymmetry costs (Frankel and Li, 2004), and I expect the breakeven R&D to be lower.

i) Corporate Governance-

Firms with better corporate governance has been shown to have lower information asymmetry costs (Cai et al. 2009 and Chung et al. 2010) and so I should expect the breakeven R&D to be lower.

j) Firm total risk-

Firms with high total risk have higher information asymmetry costs as measured by the volatility of the stock returns (Halov and Heider, 2011; Krishnaswamy and Subramaniam,

1999; Diamond, 1991; Sufi, 2007) and so I expect firms to have higher R&D break-even levels.

4. CONCLUSION

In this paper, I try to propose a simple way to determine the implicit information asymmetry costs of a project manifested in the share price of a firm's common stock. As far as I know, no other paper has analyzed these costs, focusing only on the benefits of R&D investments. I suggest in this paper that information asymmetry costs will start high and then fall while the benefits will start low and then rise. The point where the costs and benefits curve intersect is the breakeven point of R&D expenses. I then point out some moderating variables that may affect the curves. Managers reluctant to invest big sums in research due to the uncertain nature of the R&D should find this research very helpful. Grouping projects into high risk, medium and low risk based upon the information asymmetry costs will aid managers tackle uncertainty.

5. FUTURE RESEARCH AND LIMITATIONS

This paper gives various rich avenues for future research. First, my methodology of calculating costs can be tested using real stock price data. I should expect the graph to look identical based upon my theoretical perspective. Similar projects for a firm should also have similar cost and benefit curves assuming market efficiency and rational investors. Second, further empirical tests will also show how the moderating factors affect the curves as mentioned in the paper. The biggest limitation of this paper is not using stock data to test the theory in real life projects. For example, the curves might show a concave/convex structure rather than a linear curve. Also, the slope of the lines might be different. Another limitation is not suggesting a specific cost model but rather using the consensus view of the market to determine the costs. I go this route using line of thought that "the market is always right" but as we know sometimes investors act irrationally which will cause the curves to differ from their original shapes.

REFERENCES

- [1] Baber, W. R., Fairfield, P. M., & Haggard, J. A. (1991). The effect of concern about reported income on discretionary spending decisions: The case of research and development. *Accounting Review*, 818-829.
- [2] Balakrishnan, K., Billings, M. B., Kelly, B., & Ljungqvist, A. (2014). Shaping liquidity: On the causal effects of voluntary disclosure. *the Journal of Finance*, 69(5), 2237-2278.

-
- [3] Billings, M. B., Jennings, R., & Lev, B. (2015). On guidance and volatility. *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 60(2-3), 161-180.
- [4] Cai, J., Liu, Y., Qian, Y., & Yu, M. (2015). Information asymmetry and corporate governance. *Quarterly Journal of Finance*, 5(03), 1550014.
- [5] Cao, J., Hsieh, S., & Kohlbeck, M. (2013). Major customers and management earnings forecasts. Working paper. Florida Atlantic University.
- [6] Chan, L. K., Lakonishok, J., & Sougiannis, T. (2001). The stock market valuation of research and development expenditures. *The Journal of finance*, 56(6), 2431-2456.
- [7] Chan, S. H., Martin, J. D., & Kensinger, J. W. (1990). Corporate research and development expenditures and share value. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 26(2), 255-276.
- [8] Cheng, B., Ioannou, I., & Serafeim, G. (2014). Corporate social responsibility and access to finance. *Strategic management journal*, 35(1), 1-23.
- [9] Chung, K. H., Elder, J., & Kim, J. C. (2010). Corporate governance and liquidity. *Journal of financial and quantitative analysis*, 45(2), 265-291.
- [10] Coller, M., & Yohn, T. L. (1997). Management forecasts and information asymmetry: An examination of bid-ask spreads. *Journal of accounting research*, 35(2), 181-191.
- [11] Connolly, R. A., & Hirschey, M. (1990). Firm size and R&D effectiveness: a value-based test. *Economics Letters*, 32(3), 277-281.
- [12] Cui, J., Jo, H., & Na, H. (2018). Does corporate social responsibility affect information asymmetry?. *Journal of business ethics*, 148(3), 549-572.
- [13] Diamond, D. (1991). Monitoring and reputation: The choice between bank loans and privately placed debt. *Journal of Political Economy*, 99 (04), 689-721.
- [14] Eberhart, A. C., Maxwell, W. F., & Siddique, A. R. (2004). An examination of long-term abnormal stock returns and operating performance following R&D increases. *The journal of finance*, 59(2), 623-650.
- [15] Feeny, S., & Rogers, M. (2003). Innovation and performance: Benchmarking Australian firms. *Australian Economic Review*, 36(3), 253-264.
- [16] Frankel, R. M., & Li, X. (2002). The characteristics of a firm's information environment and the predictive ability of insider trades. Available at SSRN 286454.
- [17] Graham, J. R., Harvey, C. R., & Rajgopal, S. (2005). The economic implications of corporate financial reporting. *Journal of accounting and economics*, 40(1-3), 3-73.
- [18] Halov, N., & Heider, F. (2011). Capital structure, risk and asymmetric information. *The Quarterly Journal of Finance*, 1(04), 767-809.

- [19] Harter, C. I., & Harikumar, T. (2004). Management compensation and project life. *Journal of Applied Business Research (JABR)*, 20(4).
- [20] Jones, D. A. (2007). Voluntary disclosure in R&D-intensive industries. *Contemporary Accounting Research*, 24(2), 489-522.
- [21] Joseph, K., & Wintoki, M. B. (2013). Advertising investments, information asymmetry, and insider gains. *Journal of Empirical Finance*, 22, 1-15.
- [22] Kothari, S. P., Laguerre, T. E., & Leone, A. J. (2002). Capitalization versus expensing: Evidence on the uncertainty of future earnings from capital expenditures versus R&D outlays. *Review of Accounting Studies*, 7(4), 355-382.
- [23] Krishnaswami, S., & Subramaniam, V. (1999). Information asymmetry, valuation, and the corporate spin-off decision. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 53(1), 73-112.
- [24] Lagrost, C., Martin, D., Dubois, C., & Quazzotti, S. (2010). Intellectual property valuation: how to approach the selection of an appropriate valuation method. *Journal of Intellectual Capital*, 11(4), 481-503.
- [25] Lakonishok, J., & Lee, I. (2001). Are insider trades informative?. *The Review of Financial Studies*, 14(1), 79-111.
- [26] Lev, B., & Sougiannis, T. (1996). The capitalization, amortization, and value-relevance of R&D. *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 21(1), 107-138.
- [27] Luo, X., Wang, H., Raithel, S., & Zheng, Q. (2015). Corporate social performance, analyst stock recommendations, and firm future returns. *Strategic Management Journal*, 36(1), 123-136.
- [28] Lys, T., Naughton, J. P., & Wang, C. (2015). Signaling through corporate accountability reporting. *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 60(1), 56-72.
- [29] Merkley, K. J. (2014). Narrative disclosure and earnings performance: Evidence from R&D disclosures. *The Accounting Review*, 89(2), 725-757.
- [30] Pastor, D., Glova, J., Lipták, F., & Kovac, V. (2017). Intangibles and methods for their valuation in financial terms: Literature review. *Intangible Capital*, 13(2), 387-410.
- [31] Porter, M. E. (1992). Capital disadvantage: America's failing capital investment system. *Harvard Business Review*, 70(5), 65-82.
- [32] Seyhun, H. N. (1986). Insiders' profits, costs of trading, and market efficiency. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 16(2), 189-212.
- [33] Sufi, A. (2007). Information asymmetry and financing arrangements: Evidence from syndicated loans. *The Journal of Finance*, 62(2), 629-668.
- [34] Wahal, S., & McConnell, J. J. (2000). Do institutional investors exacerbate managerial myopia?. *Journal of Corporate Finance*, 6(3), 307-329.